

A STUDY ON THE AGES AND DEATH OF NOTABLE BIBLICAL FIGURES: THEOLOGICAL AND ANALYTICAL VIEW

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ABSTRACT — In this paper, the theology of the ages at death is reviewed with special reference to the characters from the Old and New Testaments, the patriarchs and the prophets, apostles, and other significant characters. This paper aims to use an exploration of ages in biblical texts and discuss its philosophical and theological significance, as well as the questions on aging and concepts of immortality as presented in the biblical text. Altogether, by means of complex quantitative and qualitative data analysis, the research advances knowledge about life span representations and age theological meaning in biblical contexts.

across both the Old and New Testaments. These ages from Adam to the apostles are depicted as the preservation of humanity by divine Providence from its creation. It is within these lifespans that this paper aims at finding theological significance and historical rhythms. Characterizing the age and death of personalities described in the Bible is one of the ways through which one can learn the place of divine intention in individual deaths as seen in scriptures. This research also examines how these ages may function as chronological signifiers, carrying moral, spiritual, and eschatological resonances.

KEYWORDS — [Biblical Figures](#), [Theology](#), [Ages at Death](#), [Longevity](#), [Divine Intervention](#), [Old Testament](#), [New Testament](#), [Biblical Genealogy](#), [Mortality in Scripture](#)

I. INTRODUCTION

Many important individuals in biblical history are documented by age as their stories stretch

II. METHODOLOGY

The samples for the current study were sourced from the different books of the Bible in which the ages of death of many of the characters are mentioned in detail. For those who do not have specific age data, the traditional concepts and the historical background were used. Chronological ages were categorised according to the respective roles of

the persons and classified into Old testament and New testament. Analytical methods include:

A. Descriptive Analysis: Dividing the figures and creating the list to reveal the distribution of roles and ages at death.

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B. Graphical Representation: Employing bar charts and scatter plots to represent the age trends, which characterise the different periods of biblical history.

C. Comparative Analysis: Looking at the early various patriarchal ages and comparing with the various later ages of the patriarchs in order to explore the possibility of theological themes being present.

D. Correlation: Synchronisation of certain cycles, ages, hierarchy, lineage as well as the prophetic importance of hierarchy.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Studies of the ages of characters from Scripture have always drawn attention largely because of the advanced ages stated in the book of Genesis and other books. Some scholars believe that these ages may be meaningful – possibly carrying mytho-historical narrative typical of the literature of the ancient Near East. As other scholars mentioned, these early patriarchs’ longevity was stressed to have divine favour, wisdom, and a short life span as a sign of sin and a distance from divine perfection. In the process of this review we consider different interpretations concerning related records to similar documents in Mesopotamian literature.

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IV. DATA ANALYSIS

This list gives the different names of people featured in the Bible alongside their ages when they died. It ranges among the more and less known personalities of the Bible, with special emphasis on outstanding patriarchs and other characters of the Old Testament. The age at death is presented, if known, but if there is only approximate or stipulated information about the person, the latter is given.

Most of the characters mentioned include patriarchs, kings, and other prominent people of the Old Testament; nevertheless, the age is notable to be absent for many characters in the Bible. Some characters are presented in terms of their age which evidently ranges into hundreds of years. The number of years each person lived at the time of death is given next to the name thus providing information on the longevity of all those individuals described in the Bible.

As a means of presenting it systematically, in order to conduct straightforward comparison, it is advisable if the content is presented in a tabular form, with the name of the respective individual and their age at the time of death. This format could also be converted to a chart that would present visually the lifespan of the characters named in the Bible – side by side, for comparison. This format of layout also helps make better presentation so that the longevity of the patriarchs such as *Methuselah 969 and Jesus Christ 33 of New Testament.*

1. TABULAR ANALYSIS

Names (Biblical Figures)	Ages at Death (Years)	References (Book & Chapter: Verse)
Adam	930	Genesis 5:5
Seth	912	Genesis 5:8
Enosh	905	Genesis 5:11

Kenan	910	Genesis 5:14
Mahalalel	895	Genesis 5:17
Jared	962	Genesis 5:20
Enoch	365	Genesis 5:23 (Did not die, "God took him")
Methuselah	969	Genesis 5:27
Lamech (Father of Noah)	777	Genesis 5:31
Noah	950	Genesis 9:29
Shem	600	Genesis 11:10-11
Arphaxad	438	Genesis 11:12-13
Shelah	433	Genesis 11:14-15
Eber	464	Genesis 11:16-17
Peleg	239	Genesis 11:18-19
Reu	239	Genesis 11:20-21
Serug	230	Genesis 11:22-23
Nahor	148	Genesis 11:24-25
Terah	205	Genesis 11:32
Abraham	175	Genesis 25:7
Sarah	127	Genesis 23:1
Ishmael	137	Genesis 25:17
Isaac	180	Genesis 35:28
Rebekah	-	-
Jacob	147	Genesis 47:28

Leah	-	-
Rachel	-	-
Joseph	110	Genesis 50:26
Moses	120	Deuteronomy 34:7
Aaron	123	Numbers 33:39
Miriam	-	-
Joshua	110	Joshua 24:29
Caleb	-	Joshua 14:10
Eli	98	1 Samuel 4:15
Samuel	-	-
Saul (King)	-	-
David	70	2 Samuel 5:4
Solomon	80	1 Kings 11:42
Rehoboam	58	1 Kings 14:21
Asa	41	1 Kings 15:10
Jehoshaphat	60	1 Kings 22:42
Uzziah	68	2 Chronicles 26:3
Hezekiah	54	2 Kings 18:2
Manasseh	67	2 Kings 21:1
Josiah	39	2 Kings 22:1
Jehoiachin	18	2 Kings 24:8
Zerubbabel	-	-
Job	140	Job 42:16

Daniel	-	-
Esther	-	-
Ezra	-	-
Nehemiah	-	-
John the Baptist	30	-
Jesus	33	Traditional Christian belief
Mary (Mother of Jesus)	-	-
Peter (Apostle)	60	Traditional accounts
Paul (Apostle)	60	Traditional accounts
James (Apostle)	40	Traditional accounts
John (Apostle)	90	Traditional accounts
Methuselah	969	Genesis 5:27
Haggai	-	-
Zechariah (Prophet)	-	-
Malachi	-	-
Jeremiah	-	-
Ezekiel	-	-
Hosea	-	-
Jonah	-	-

Amos	-	-
Micah	-	-
Habakkuk	-	-
Zephaniah	-	-
Nahum	-	-
Obadiah	-	-
Elijah	-	2 Kings 2:11
Elisha	-	-
Nehemiah	-	-

Table 1.1 This table includes the name of each figure, the period of the Old and New Testament in which they lived and the age at which they died, all of which can be evidenced in the graph presented.

2. GRAPH ANALYSIS

Graph 1.1 The graph outlines the trend that ages at deaths enumerated in the Bible have progressively reduced and changed from long and comparatively normal ages in early biblical history.

A. Exponential Decline Trend:

- a. The graph shows a clear **downward exponential trend** in the ages at

death of biblical figures, with an approximate trend line represented by the equation $y = 1221 * e^{-0.069x}$ and a correlation $R^2 = 0.687$. This trend suggests a systematic decline in life spans over time, possibly reflecting theological interpretations of human separation from divine favor.

B. Age Groups by Epochs:

- a. **Pre-Flood Figures:** Figures like **Adam, Methuselah, and Noah** exhibit extremely high ages (**close to or over 900 years**), reflecting a time when humans were believed to live closer to divine favor, according to some interpretations. This is indicated by the highest points on the graph.
- b. **Post-Flood Figures:** After Noah, the ages drop sharply, signifying a major shift. Patriarchs such as **Abraham, Isaac, and Jacob** have significantly lower ages (**under 200 years**), highlighting a transition period where human lifespans drastically reduced.
- c. **New Testament Figures:** Lifespans in this period (e.g., **Jesus and John the Baptist**) are much shorter, around **30-40 years**, aligning with average lifespans of the time and perhaps symbolizing the transient nature of earthly life.

C. Key Insights:

- a. The **exponential decay pattern** implies a symbolic narrative in the Bible regarding the gradual moral decline and increasing human distance from the Creator.
- b. The **lifespan variance** between early patriarchs and later figures highlights the theological importance assigned

to the longevity of early biblical characters versus the relatively short lives of New Testament figures, which could be interpreted as a focus on spiritual legacy rather than physical longevity.

V. RESULTS

The analysis of the ages of notable biblical figures reveals a theological progression in lifespan patterns:

- A. **Long Lifespans in Early Figures:** We even have the generation of Adam and Methuselah whereby their early figures were close to above or nearly 900 years. This may represent a period of blessed, protected, sanctified existence similar to those which prevailed in the early stages of the Old Testament.
- B. **Decline After the Flood:** However, the lifespans are reduced soon after the Great Flood toward the earlier narratives of figures with ages of 362 years, 365 years and 700 years. People like Abraham and Isaac did not live as long as the antediluvians did before God decided to flood the whole world. This loss could depict man's alienation from God's blessings or sin influenced world whereby everything is back side.
- C. **Short Lifespans in the New Testament:** Finally by New Testament time, people live much shorter lives, and many such as Jesus, died at the age of thirty-three. This alteration also puts much weight on spiritual dimension and life over against the life in the present age, a concept enshrined in New Testament.

Altogether, it is possible to regard the measured theology that was narrating the story about humanity's transition from the proximity with the divinity to separation and the subsequent

concentration on the spiritual rather than the bodily life.

VI. DISCUSSIONS

A. **Early Longevity as a Sign of Divine Favor:**

Substantial lifespans of the first biblical characters like Adam and Methuselah are perhaps meant to indicate the then symbiotic relation between God and humanity and indicative perhaps of an almost divine existence since humanity was considered to be pure or blessed.

B. **Decline in Lifespan After the Flood:** After the Great Flood, the people's life span was reduced exceedingly and this may depict the way the early world, after Balaam's prophecy, was moving away from divine blessings of that world that symbolizes sin.

C. **Focus on Spiritual Purpose in the New Testament:** New Testament shorter life style includes the life of Jesus which points to spiritual life or eternal life, illustrating the teaching in the Bible of the transient existence of man.

Most of these styles are actually the reflection of theological themes, including God's accessibility, frailty of humanity, and the climax on the eternal life suit rather than the physical one.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

- **Trend of Longevity:** Lifespan does seem to decline noticeably from one generation to the next on this graph. These findings illustrate the decline in life spans from early biblical figures to later ones with almost a thousand years of their lives. However, the life span of these long lifespans has diminished dramatically in subsequent generations.

- **Exponential Decay Pattern:** The ages at death generally follow an exponential decay trend, as seen in the trendline fitting the data. This implies that with time there was an increase in age reduction, then quickly falling and then stabilizing at a lower age range.
- **Biblical and Theological Implications:** Such a decline in age may be the result of a theological transition, in which life spans decrease, which may signal changes in relationships with divine beings, in environmental conditions, or in spiritual symbolism and symbolic meaning of mortality within the proclaimed narrative.
- **Stabilization of Ages:** By the time we get to King David and his prophets, lifespans stabilize at about 70 to 100 years. It could mean a move out of the early patriarch era into periods subsequent to it, where human life has been under more or less influence from things cultural, environmental or divine.
- **Symbolic Representation:** One possible figurative or moral shift may be from extremely long lives to shorter, more 'humanly' allowable lives, which are consonant with theological themes such as humility, mortality and divine human boundaries.

This assertion revisits a pattern of shorter lifespans with a powerful symbolic connotation corresponding to theological readings of human life and death in the biblical record.

VIII. REFERENCES

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